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Open Science Guidebook: Open Workflows

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Advances in information technology have created possibilities to share digital scholarly objects in ways that were not feasible before. In recent years, much of the focus of the Open Science movement has been on broadening the access to different research outputs, primarily publications and data. However, as new technical tools and internet are increasingly liberating researchers from the communication limitations of a traditional research paper, more and more attention is being given to the transparency and reusability of research workflows.

1. WHAT

On a general level, a workflow can be understood as an organized series of steps designed for achieving a particular result. A research workflow, then, refers to a set of actions taken, routines followed, decisions made, and tools utilized over the course of a research project. Open research workflows entail that researchers embrace and extend the Open Science principles to the entire research cycle and organize and carry out their work in a transparent, replicable and reproducible manner. Essentially, transparent and repeatable workflows require that each step of the research process is comprehensively documented and explicitly represented to facilitate verification and understandability of the results and reasoning behind them, to improve reuse utility of the used methods and data, and to enhance replicability and reproducibility of research.

Instead of a single Open Science practice, open workflows can be understood as varying collections of behaviours with the common aim of making research process transparent at each of its steps. It is important to note, however, that open workflows do not suggest exposing research. While the eventual target in all research should be shareability of the workflow to the public, in many cases, sharing e.g., data or materials prior to publication may be out of question. Key factors for open workflows are clear and thorough documentation of how research is conducted and provision of access to information and materials needed to reproduce the procedures and analyses and to understand the choices made. Components of the workflow vary across disciplines and contexts, but examples include instruments, data, tools, methods, code and scripts. While open workflows are approached differently depending on the discipline and context, the general idea of keeping an organized record of the process and being able to communicate its steps meaningfully to others is applicable to any research across all disciplines.

Numerous dedicated tools now exist for workflow management. These tools allow setting up a public or a private project page with cloud storage space for different types of project files. Their other important features include version control and time stamping of digital objects and possibility to share the project with others ability to control who has access to the content. Furthermore, online workflow repositories can be assigned their own DOI (digital object identifier) making it possible for others to cite the project.

2. WHY

Open workflows are emerging as a practice that significantly enhances transparency and reproducibility of research. Open workflows are essential for enabling others to understand the context and reasonings behind decisions and choices of the researcher and on the other hand replicate and refine the research process. Open workflows also encourage researchers to employ standard structures for e.g., data and code archiving. However, implementation of open workflows varies based on context, and depending on the discipline, greatest benefits may relate to e.g., preregistration, code, data, methods or results. Finally, open workflows may improve efficiency of research. Especially, script-based workflows are infinitely reusable and transferable to other datasets bringing significant time savings.

From a researcher's perspective, careful recordkeeping through the course of a research project helps to keep the project organised, minimises errors, provides protection against losses of valuable information, and contributes to long-term preservation of research outputs for others but also for one's own purposes. Letting others to view and evaluate the research project while it is still ongoing allows for detecting errors, providing and incorporating feedback which can be beneficial in terms of quality of research and lead to more robust research results. Furthermore, open sharing of the workflows before publication to others in an online repository increases visibility of one's work, allows for receiving credit in the form of citations, may facilitate new and unexpected collaboration.

3. HOW

For those who are interested in getting started with open workflows, it would be useful to note the following points:

- As you plan the steps of your work it might be useful to centralize and organize your project management using an online platform, a central repository, or folder for all research files.
- Workflow repositories, such as Open Science Framework (OSF) or GitHub, provide a structure for sharing your research openly and help you to manage, control access, archive, and share each step of your research project.
- Use of open licenses and persistent identifiers facilitates reuse by others and helps to protect one's work and receive credit for it.
- Using open-source software or proprietary software that uses open file formats facilitates accessibility to other researchers, supports interoperability and provides protection against future losses of valuable information due to end of support for a particular custom file format.

RESOURCES AND FURTHER READING

- Workflow management tools:
 - Open Science Framework: <https://osf.io/>
 - GitHub: <https://github.com/>
- Tool for choosing a licence:
 - <https://choosealicense.com/>
- 101innovations website:
 - <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/>
- Hampton, S.E. et al. (2015) 'The Tao of open science for ecology', *Ecosphere*, 6(7), pp. 1-22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1890/ES14-00402.1>.
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